

Charge localization and trapping at surfaces in lead-iodide perovskites: the role of polarons and defects

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Abstract

Surfaces and grain boundaries play a fundamental role in charge transport, localization and trapping in polycrystalline thin films of metal halide perovskites. Comprehension of the phenomena occurring at the surface is thus crucial to increase solar cell efficiency and, most importantly, temporal stability. We investigate charge localization and trapping at the surface of the prototypical MAPbI₃ perovskite through advanced electronic-structure calculations, considering different surface terminations. Both MAI- and PbI₂-terminated surfaces exhibit a clear spatial separation of hole and electron polarons, while a MAI-vacant surface induces charge localization at under-coordinated lead atoms. Notably, the PbI₂-terminated surface is sensitive to surface defects, which may either act as recombination centres or inhibit charge transfer at the surface, while the MAI-terminated surface is comparably more defect tolerant. We thus suggest that perovskite growth under MAI-rich conditions should be beneficial to limit surface recombination, while the synthesis of MAPbI₃ in a PbI₂-rich environment should be accompanied by surface passivation strategies to counteract the negative impact of surface defects.

1. Introduction

Metal halide perovskites of general formula ABX₃ have generated an unprecedented excitement in the growing field of third-generation photovoltaics.¹⁻³ Since the pioneering studies only ten years ago, the photo-conversion efficiency of devices based on metal halide perovskites has rocketed from 4% (ref. 4) to >25%,⁵ a growth rate unequalled by other prospective materials for solar cells that have been investigated during the same time span. The extraordinary results achieved by this novel class of materials may provide a viable solution to complement or even replace silicon-based solar cells in the near future. However, the fulfilment of such a goal is related to an in-depth comprehension of the electronic and stability properties of metal halide perovskites, which have eluded both measurements and theory for a long time. In particular, one of the key features behind the success of metal halide perovskites is the slow recombination of photogenerated carriers measured for both the most common mechanisms: *i.e.* (i) band-to-band transitions (bimolecular recombination) and (ii) transitions mediated by defects (monomolecular recombination).⁶⁻¹⁰ This peculiar property has for long puzzled the scientific community. Therefore, large efforts have been devoted to explain how these atypical materials could match the performance of high-purity inorganic crystalline semiconductors.^{11,12} Early attempts of explaining the slow bimolecular recombination measured for lead halide perovskites focussed on the possible role of the organic A-site cations in screening the photogenerated excitons^{13,14} or in favouring a different localization of valence and conduction band-edge states.^{15,16} However, bimolecular recombination coefficients measured for fully inorganic perovskites were found to be close to those of related perovskites bearing organic cations,¹⁷ thus ruling out these explanations. The slow monomolecular recombination measured for these materials was

even more puzzling. In fact, low-temperature techniques used to synthesize metal halide perovskites are likely to provide a high concentration of intrinsic defects,¹⁸⁻²⁰ some of which, in turn, are predicted by theory to play a role in charge trapping and recombination.²¹ Nonetheless, these materials appear to be defect-tolerant.²²⁻²⁴ Recent time-resolved Kerr-effect spectroscopy measurements and first-principles calculations indicated that charge carriers in lead halide perovskites may occur as large polarons,^{25,26} casting some light on the physical origin of the exceptional opto-electronic properties of lead halide perovskites. Polaron formation was found to occur on the sub-picosecond timescale,^{25,26} and therefore not compatible with the rotation of the organic cations. Furthermore, advanced molecular dynamics simulations performed on MAPbI₃ (MA = methylammonium) have shown that hole and electron polarons are rapidly separated in different regions of the material, upon photoexcitation. This feature is found to decrease the recombination rate by at least one order of magnitude against that pertinent to band-to-band transitions.²⁶ The polaronic nature of charge carriers could also contribute to the defect tolerance of MAPbI₃; hole and electron recombination at interstitial iodine defects may be limited by the synergistic effects of a small kinetic barrier and of the screened interaction between the hole polaron and the negatively charged iodine defect.²⁷ Finally, very recent *ab initio* calculations have revealed further insights on the nature of polarons in lead halide perovskites, as they are found to depend on a delicate balance between thermally induced disorder, driven by the motion of A-site cations, and polaron stabilization within the BX₃ sublattice.²⁸ A detailed investigation of polaron hopping within the material pointed out a mechanism guided by the random reorientation of the A-site cations,²⁸ which allowed the explanation of the observed low mobility²⁹ and high diffusion length of charge carriers.^{10,30,31}

Although the comprehension of the outstanding properties of lead halide perovskites has seen remarkable advancements, further improvements of devices based on these materials are indeed possible, since the current efficiencies are still noticeably smaller than that predicted by the Shockley–Queisser limit.³² In this regard, while most studies have focussed on the electronic properties of bulk materials, channels for charge loss and instabilities in working devices could originate from phenomena occurring at the thin film surface and at device interfaces.^{33,34} It is well known that the surface of solution-processed lead halide perovskites is prone to the formation of defects, which could be noxious for the opto-electronic properties of devices.³⁵⁻³⁸ In fact, surface trap density was found to be up to two orders of magnitude larger than that of the bulk material and the diffusion length of charge carriers was noticeably shorter.³⁹ Time-resolved spectroscopy measurements have shown that the surface recombination velocity in polycrystalline films is nearly an order of magnitude smaller than that in single crystals, an instance possibly justified by defect passivation operated by the excess of MA in non-stoichiometric samples.³⁷ In contrast, *ab initio* calculations performed by Tong *et al.* indicated MA to be responsible for charge recombination at the surface and suggested that decreasing its concentration on the surface would be beneficial for the system.⁴⁰ Similarly, density functional theory (DFT) calculations performed on different models of MAPbI₃ indicate that a PbI₂-rich condition would favour flat surfaces without mid-gap states.^{41,42} A large number of studies have focussed on the role of passivating layers on top of the surface, as they could minimize surface recombination,⁴³⁻⁴⁷ possibly also extending the stability of the device. Furthermore, surface termination can also determine a different alignment of energy levels at the interface, depending on the charge transfer layers used in the device. For example, it has been found that the favourable alignment between MAI-covered surfaces and C₆₀ promotes electron transfer across the MAPbI₃/C₆₀ interface.⁴⁸ However, when a hole-transport material such as spiro-MeO-TAD is considered, the shift of the band edges towards the vacuum level induced by surface MAI hinders the hole transfer process.⁴⁹ Overall, since the physics of charge carriers at the surface is not completely understood, the design of viable solutions to simultaneously limit charge recombination and enhance charge transfer across the interface is lacking a rationale. Furthermore, current studies do not account for the polaronic nature of charge carriers, which could play a key role not only in the bulk but also on surfaces.

In this work, we study the electronic properties of the (001) surface of tetragonal MAPbI₃ by hybrid DFT calculations. Our analysis shows that hole and electron polarons localize in different spatial regions in pristine PbI₂-terminated (PbI₂) and MAI-terminated (MAI) (001) surfaces. The reduced spatial overlap of electrons and holes hinders their recombination on these surfaces. On the other hand, for systems with a partial MAI coverage, hole and electron polarons appear to be spatially closer, and thus the probability of recombination is enhanced. Furthermore, we observe the formation of a small electron polaron on the partially MAI-covered surface associated with a surface reconstruction around an unsaturated Pb ion on the surface, indicating that charge-trapping processes are further enhanced on this surface. These results suggest that rough surfaces with a partial coverage may severely affect the efficiency of perovskite-based devices by promoting both radiative and non-radiative recombination through localized surface states.

To further investigate the sources of non-radiative recombination, we include in our study the analysis of the stability and the trapping activity of native defects at these surfaces. By comparing the formation energies of surface and bulk defects, we observe that only the MA vacancy (V_{MA}), which produces a shallow energy level, is favoured on the MAI surface. In contrast, vacancies of Pb (V_{Pb}) and I (V_I) and the I interstitial (I_i) are more stable on the PbI₂-terminated surface. In particular, V_{Pb} and I_i , which feature mid-gap transition energy levels, can promote monomolecular charge recombination. Furthermore, the study of I_i shows that hole trapping on this defect involves the crossing of an energy barrier for both considered surface terminations, in line with previous results achieved for the bulk material.²⁷ The different spatial localization of holes and electrons on the surfaces, however, significantly enhances the probability of hole trapping at defects in the PbI₂-terminated surface with respect to the MAI-terminated surface and bulk MAPbI₃. In contrast, surface V_I defects, while not directly acting as recombination centres, do not support the formation of a hole polaron within the PbI₂ layer bearing it. This might prevent the migration of hole polarons on the surface, an occurrence which would likely be detrimental for interfacial charge transfer at selective contacts.

Finally, the consequences of the present results are discussed in view of the ongoing efforts to limit interfacial charge recombination and enhance charge transfer. On one side, synthesis of MAPbI₃ in a MAI-rich environment may be a satisfactory strategy for limiting the formation of PbI₂-rich surfaces, responsible for the increased monomolecular recombination, without affecting the defect tolerance of perovskite polycrystalline films. On the other hand, this should be coupled to a judicious choice of materials used as charge transport layers, in order to achieve an optimal alignment of energy levels.⁴⁹

2. Methods

All DFT calculations are carried out at the hybrid-functional level with the PBE0 functional.^{50,51} The fraction of Fock exchange α is preserved to its original value (0.25), because it complies with the Koopmans condition for this material,⁵² thus ensuring that the calculations are essentially devoid of the self-interaction error,^{26,53,54} which would affect the energetics of the system and charge localization. We include non-local van der Waals interactions through the rVV10 scheme.^{55,56} Calculations are carried out with the freely-available CP2K suite of codes.⁵⁷ Goedecker–Teter–Hutter pseudopotentials are used to account for core-valence interactions.⁵⁸ We use double- ζ polarized basis sets for the wave functions⁵⁹ and a cut-off of 300 Ry for the expansion of the electron density in plane waves. We employ the auxiliary density matrix method to speed up the calculation of exact exchange in hybrid functional calculations as implemented in CP2K with the cFIT auxiliary basis set.⁶⁰ We do not include spin-orbit coupling (SOC) in geometry optimizations, as this is not implemented in CP2K. While significantly contributing to the electronic properties of lead-halide perovskites^{61,62} the effect of SOC on valence band-edge states is rather limited.⁶³ This ensures that the properties of hole polarons, originating from the valence band, are properly captured by our computational approach. Furthermore, even if the position of the conduction band-edge states is noticeably influenced by SOC,^{61,62} previous studies have shown that the introduction of SOC has negligible effects on polaron localization²⁶ and on the calculated stabilization energies.⁶⁴ However, in one particular case (*vide infra*),

additional calculations including SOC are carried out to properly describe an electron polaron, whose energetics is indeed sensitive to SOC. Calculations are performed on different models of the (001) surface of tetragonal $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$: (i) a 552 atoms slab terminated with methylammonium iodide (MAI) (cf. Fig. 1, left panel), (ii) a 408 atoms slab terminated with lead diiodide (PbI_2) (cf. Fig. 1, right panel) and (iii) slabs with a partial MAI coverage. All the considered slabs possess the same thickness (five PbI_2 layers), and the simulation cell has $a = b = 17.70 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 50 \text{ \AA}$, with the latter including a vacuum layer of 20 (25) \AA for the MAI (PbI_2) slab, a computational setup that has been benchmarked in previous studies.⁴⁹ In particular, we note that the position of band edges is stable with respect to the slab thickness. This implies that the energetics of defects, which is influenced by the position of band edges, is not affected by the slab thickness.⁴⁹ Furthermore, in the ESI,[†] we verify that charge localization and the energetics of polarons are unaffected by the thickness of the slab, by performing extra calculations using slabs with six and seven PbI_2 layers. We note that a previous study on polarons in the bulk material has shown that convergence of the charge density is achieved only when considering very large supercells ($>80 \text{ \AA}$).⁶⁵ However, the effect of size on the energetics of polarons was found to be rather exiguous.²⁸ This ensures that the trends observed in this study are not affected by the employed supercell. We focus on the (001) surface since both theoretical calculations^{41,66} and X-ray diffraction experiments⁶⁷ indicate that this is one of the dominant facets in tetragonal MAPbI_3 . Additional calculations of defects performed for bulk tetragonal MAPbI_3 are carried out by employing a 384 atoms $2 \times 2 \times 2$ supercell with lattice parameters $a = b = 17.72 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 25.32 \text{ \AA}$.

Fig. 1 Stick & ball representation of the PbI_2 and MAI (001) surfaces of tetragonal MAPbI_3 . Lead in brown, iodine in pink, nitrogen in blue, carbon in cyan, and hydrogen in white.

To calculate the energy levels of polarons and defects in the slabs of MAPbI_3 , we adopt the grand-canonical formulation of defects in crystalline materials.^{68,69} This theory allows us to express the formation energy of a defect X with charge q , $E_f^q[X]$ as a function of the electron chemical potential μ :

$$E_r^q[X] = E^q[X] - E[\text{ref}] - \sum_i n_i \mu_i + q(\varepsilon_v + \mu) + E_{\text{corr}}^q \quad (1)$$

In [eqn \(1\)](#), $E^q[X]$ is the total energy of the defect X in the charge state q , $E[\text{ref}]$ is the total energy of the pristine slab, μ_i is the chemical potential of the subtracted/added species i , ε_v is the valence band edge of the pristine system, and E_{corr}^q is a correction term, here introduced to account for electrostatic finite-size effects of charged periodic supercells. The charge transition level $\mu(q/q')$ is defined as the electron chemical potential for which the formation energies of a defect X in the charge states q and q' are equal ($E_r^q[X] = E_r^{q'}[X]$):

$$\mu(q/q') = \frac{E^q[X] - E^{q'}[X]}{q' - q} + \frac{E_{\text{corr}}^q - E_{\text{corr}}^{q'}}{q' - q} - \varepsilon_v. \quad (2)$$

To calculate the binding energies of hole and electron polarons, we consider the following reactions, respectively:

From [eqn \(3\)](#) and [\(4\)](#), the hole and electron polaron levels can then be defined as follows, respectively:

$$\mu(h_{\text{loc}}) = E[h_{\text{loc}}] - E[\text{MAPbI}_3] + E_{\text{corr}}^{+1} - \varepsilon_v, \quad (5)$$

$$\mu(e_{\text{loc}}) = E[e_{\text{loc}}] - E[\text{MAPbI}_3] + E_{\text{corr}}^{-1} - \varepsilon_v, \quad (6)$$

where $E[h_{\text{loc}}]$ and $E[e_{\text{loc}}]$ are the total energies of the hole and electron polarons, respectively, and $E[\text{MAPbI}_3]$ is the total energy of the pristine slab. Then, we define the polaron binding energies as $E_b(h^+) = \mu(h_{\text{loc}})$ and $E_b(e^-) = \varepsilon_c - \mu(e_{\text{loc}})$ where ε_c is the conduction band edge of the pristine slab.

Electrostatic finite size corrections for slabs are here taken into account, using the Freysoldt–Neugebauer–Van de Walle (FNV) scheme.^{68,70} The FNV correction has two contributions: (i) the Madelung energy, which accounts for the monopole charge subject to periodic boundary conditions and (ii) an alignment-like term, due to the finite extent of the charge distribution, which is computed from the shift of the average electrostatic potential with respect to the pristine bulk system in a region far from the defect. For charged slabs, we use the method developed for surfaces and interfaces by Komsa and Pasquarello.⁷¹ Within this scheme, we are able to separate (i) the spurious interactions between the periodically repeated charges and (ii) the interactions between physical image charges, occurring because of the variation in the dielectric constant across the surface. In particular, we calculate the energy correction $E_{\text{corr}}^q = E_{\text{iso}} - E_{\text{per}} + q\Delta V$, where E_{per} is the electrostatic energy calculated for a model representing the employed supercell, E_{iso} is the electrostatic energy obtained when uniformly scaling all the dimensions of the supercell, and ΔV is the shift in the electrostatic potential between the model and the DFT calculation.⁷¹ We here calculate E_{corr}^q up to

0.35 eV, where this maximum value is calculated for the slab bearing a surface Pb vacancy with $q = -2$. We underline that correction terms are obtained considering the static dielectric constant of $\text{MAPbI}_3 \epsilon_0 = 24$, as calculated from DFT calculations. In fact, since we do not account here for dynamical degrees of freedom, the experimental value (~ 70 from [ref. 86](#)), in which the effect of the freely rotating cations is included, would overestimate the charge screening.

Calculations of energy barriers for hole trapping on interstitial iodide are carried out using a modified version of the linear transit method²² previously employed in [ref. 28](#). The coordinates of the two neighbouring polaronic structures R_i and R_j are linearly interpolated²² according to the following expression: $R_\lambda = \lambda R_i + (1 - \lambda) R_j$ where λ is the coupling parameter connecting the two models. The achieved structures are then allowed to undergo structural relaxation in which the organic cations are free to relax. In contrast, the positions of the atoms belonging to the inorganic sub-lattice are fixed. In this way, we avoid unstable and highly energetic structures due to the linear interpolation of the coordinates of the organic cations.

3. Results and discussion

For each considered system, we performed structural relaxations in the presence of an extra hole and an extra electron. In [Table 1](#), we report the calculated values of $E_b(\text{h}^+)$ and $E_b(\text{e}^-)$. For the MAI surface, we observe hole polaron formation in an inner PbI_2 plane layer of the slab [*cf.* [Fig. 2\(a\)](#)]. The calculated $E_b(\text{h}^+)$ is 80 meV, essentially equivalent to that calculated for the bulk.²⁶ The localization is accompanied by a contraction of Pb–I bonds in the plane, in accord with the anti-bonding nature of the valence band edge states.^{26,73} In particular, the Pb–I bonds of the PbI_4 units undergo a contraction of up to 0.1 Å with respect to the neutral system. In contrast, a complete localization of the hole polaron on the surface is observed for the PbI_2 system, which is associated with an $E_b(\text{h}^+)$ of 120 meV [*cf.* [Fig. 2\(c\)](#)], consistent with the larger distortions of under-coordinated surface atoms. In fact, not only the Pb–I bonds of the surface PbI_2 layer are subject to contraction up to 0.12 Å, slightly larger than those observed for the MAI surface, but we also observe small (up to 0.05 Å) out-of-plane elongation of Pb–I bonds formed by surface Pb and bridging I atoms. Furthermore, the removal of MAI from the surface pushes the valence band towards lower energies (*i.e.* further away from the vacuum level).^{48,49} Therefore, surface valence states due to unsaturated lead atoms are found to be detached from the valence band maximum (VBM) and, therefore, favour hole localization. We note, for instance, that for a 0.5 MAI covered surface, the hole is found to be partially localized on the surface [*cf.* [Fig. 2\(b\)](#)], in line with this physical picture.

Table 1 Calculated values of $E_b(\text{h}^+)$ and $E_b(\text{e}^-)$ for different models of the (001) MAPbI_3 surface. All values are given in meV. In parentheses, we indicate whether the polaron is in the bulk region (B) or on the surface (S) of the slab

Surface	$E_b(\text{h}^+)$	$E_b(\text{e}^-)$
MAI	90 (B)	90 (S)
V_{MAI}	80 (B)	250 (S)
0.5 MAI	70 (S)	120 (S)
PbI_2	120 (S)	20 (B)

Fig. 2 Isodensity representations of an extra hole (purple, upper panels) for the (a) MAI surface, (b) 50% MAI-covered surface, and (c) PbI_2 surface. Isodensity representations of an extra electron (green, lower panels) for the (d) MAI surface, (e) MAI-vacant surface (V_{MAI}), and (f) PbI_2 surface.

The electron polaron localizes on a sub-surface PbI_2 plane in the MAI slab [cf. Fig. 2(d)], with $E_b(e^-) = 90$ meV, slightly larger than that observed for the corresponding polaron in the bulk (60 meV from ref. 26). The localization is attained *via* an elongation of Pb-I bonds up to 0.15 \AA , which is consistent with the weak anti-bonding hybridization between $\text{Pb } 6p$ and $\text{I } 5p$ in the conduction band. Furthermore, in analogy with results achieved for the hole polaron, MAI coverage moves the conduction band closer to the vacuum level,^{48,49} which in turn causes the emergence of unoccupied surface states in the PbI_2 layer below the terminal MAI one. When the extra electron is introduced into the PbI_2 system, it appears to be semi-localized [cf. Fig. 2(f)] with a small $E_b(e^-)$ (20 meV). Also for the extra electron, we investigate the nature of polarons on surfaces with a mixed coverage. In particular, upon removal of a single MAI unit from the surface (V_{MAI}), we observe the transition from a large to a small polaron. The negative charge is localized almost completely on an under-coordinated sub-surface Pb^{2+} [cf. Fig. 2(e)] and a large $E_b(e^-)$ of 250 meV is calculated. Furthermore, a significant surface reconstruction is observed with the involved lead atom being shifted upwards by almost 0.4 \AA , thus suggesting a possible degradation mechanism of the defective surface under electron-rich conditions. We notice that a similar localization is retained up to 0.5 MAI coverage of the surface. We further extend this analysis by introducing a second electron into the system bearing a surface MAI vacancy. The second electron is also localized on the unsaturated surface Pb [as in Fig. 2(e)], which is significantly displaced from its equilibrium position in the neutral system. As the ejection of metallic lead clusters from MAPbI_3 is observed experimentally under electron-rich conditions,⁷⁴ these results indeed suggest that this degradation mechanism of MAPbI_3 can be related to electron trapping by under-coordinated Pb atoms.

Since SOC could be particularly relevant in this case, as we are adding electrons to Pb -based unoccupied states, we performed supplementary calculations with the QUANTUM ESPRESSO code⁷⁵ employing full relativistic pseudopotentials.⁷⁶ In particular, we compare the total energies of the slab featuring a single surface MAI vacancy (i) upon vertical injection of the electron E_v and (ii) after reconstruction E_r , *i.e.* the so-called stabilization energy: $E_s = E_v - E_r$. At the PBE⁷⁷ + SOC level of theory, $E_s = -0.40$ eV, and hence the polaronic structure is found to be less stable. However, at the PBE0 level, $E_s = 0.55$ eV. Finally, when both exact exchange and relativistic effects are included at the PBE0 + SOC level, $E_s = -0.1$ eV. We notice that this

value is a lower limit because the calculations at 0 K do not include thermal effects, which are known to favour the stabilization of polarons in MAPbI₃.^{26,28} Therefore, the proposed physical picture of electron localization on defective surface Pb atoms is qualitatively retained when SOC is accounted for, although the stabilization energy is significantly reduced.

By comparing the results obtained for the different systems, we observe a distinct localization of holes and electrons for the pristine PbI₂ and MAI (001) surfaces, which can reduce the probability of interaction and thus recombination of photo-generated charges. Furthermore, the charge carriers appear as large polarons, which are less sensitive to the detrimental charge-trapping processes.^{78,79} This result suggests that recombination of charge carriers should be reduced in these cases. In contrast, for a rough surface with a partial MAI coverage, we observe two phenomena that could be noxious for a perovskite-based solar cell: (i) the hole and electron appear to be both localized close to the surface and (ii) the electron localizes as a small polaron, which could promote charge trapping and hinder charge transport.^{80,81} Additionally, electron trapping at under-coordinated surface lead atoms may also promote material degradation by trapping of a second electron, which may act as a precursor in the release of lead atoms as metallic lead clusters observed in experiments.⁷⁴

To provide a comprehensive picture of possible charge trapping occurring at surfaces, we consider the physics of point defects commonly encountered in MAPbI₃. First, we focus on the Pb, I, and MA vacancies (V_{Pb} , V_I and V_{MA} respectively) on both MAI and PbI₂ slabs. For each system, we compare the formation energies of the surface defects with those calculated for the bulk (cf. Fig. 3). For the MAI slab, the terminal PbI₂ plane is covered by MAI (cf. Fig. 1). In this system, V_{MA} and V_I have been thus modelled by removing MA and I from the surface MAI layer, while V_{Pb} is created within the PbI₂ layer below it. The analysis of the calculated formation energies highlights that V_I and V_{Pb} are slightly less stable (~ 0.1 eV for the neutral defect and < 0.1 eV for the -1 charge state) than the corresponding defects in the bulk defects (cf. Fig. 3). In contrast, the surface V_{MA} is remarkably more stable (~ 0.5 eV for both 0 and -1 charge states) than the relative bulk defect. The calculated charge transition levels of these defects retain many features of the same defects in the bulk. In particular, we observe only shallow charge transition levels for V_I and V_{MA} , which are stable in the positive and negative states of charge, respectively, throughout almost the entire band gap of the material. Therefore, these surface defects should not contribute to monomolecular recombination of charge carriers. On the other hand, energy levels in the band gap are observed for V_{Pb} , which are almost equivalent to those calculated for the bulk material.⁸² When considering the PbI₂ slab (cf. Fig. 3), we note that surface V_{Pb} and V_I are noticeably more stable than the corresponding bulk defects, in stark contrast with the trends observed for the MAI surface. For V_{Pb} , the calculated $\mu(0/-2)$ lies at the mid-gap, 0.80 eV above the valence band edge, and 0.3 eV above the value achieved for the bulk. A similar trend is observed also for $\mu(0/-1)$ and $\mu(-1/-2)$ (cf. Fig. 7). Hence, the surface Pb vacancy may act as a recombination centre at the PbI₂ surface of MAPbI₃. We note that, differently from previous studies,^{84,85} the charge transition levels of bulk and surface V_{Pb} are found to lie deeper in the gap of MAPbI₃. This is due to the fact that we here employ hybrid functional calculations, which accurately describe the electronic properties of defects in MAPbI₃. Furthermore, we have here considered that the most stable structural configuration for V_{Pb}^0 features the formation of a triiodide moiety (I₃⁻) close to the vacancy site (*vide infra*), in line with previous observations made for the bulk material.⁶³

Fig. 3 Formation energies of vacancies as a function of the electron chemical potential on the (a) MAI and (b) PbI_2 (001) terminated MAPbI_3 surface. Dashed lines for the respective values calculated for the bulk material. We consider iodine medium conditions as estimated in [ref. 82](#), which correspond to $\mu_{\text{MA}} = -1.71$ eV, $\mu_{\text{Pb}} = -1.43$ eV, $\mu_{\text{I}} = -0.81$ eV. The conduction band edge is placed on the energy diagram by adding the experimental band gap⁸³ of MAPbI_3 to the valence band edge.

Structural analysis of the surface defect reveals that for the negative V_{Pb}^{2-} , Pb–I bonds involving under-coordinated I atoms around the vacancy are found to be noticeably shrunk by 0.2 Å [*cf.* [Fig. 4\(a\)](#)]. When an extra hole is added to the system bearing V_{Pb}^{2-} , a hole polaron is localized in the PbI_2 plane bearing the vacancy [*cf.* [Fig. 4\(b\)](#)]. Finally, upon injection of a second hole in the system, we observe the formation of an I_3^- moiety accompanying the localization of the charge and the oxidation of one iodine. This is achieved upon migration of the surface I atom towards the vacancy [*cf.* [Fig. 4\(c\)](#)]. We note that the structural configuration of surface V_{Pb}^0 bearing I_3^- is 0.8 eV more stable than the one in which the triiodide is not formed, therefore noticeably lowering the formation energy of the defect. Furthermore, the increased stability of the surface V_{Pb}^0 on the PbI_2 surface, which is mainly responsible for the deeper charge transition levels with respect to the bulk, is due to both electronic and structural effects: in fact, since holes are found to be drawn towards the PbI_2 surface, their localization on the surface defect is energetically more favourable. Furthermore, the structural analysis reveals that the surface triiodide formed in V_{Pb}^0 is less distorted than the bulk one, thus motivating the difference in formation energies between bulk and surface defects observed in [Fig. 3\(b\)](#) (*cf.* [ESI[†]](#) for a detailed comparison of the local structures of bulk and surface V_{Pb}^0).

Fig. 4 (a) Top view of the surface reconstruction on the PbI_2 plane of the (001) surface of tetragonal MAPbI_3 for V_{Pb} in the -2 charge state. We only show one plane of Pb and I atoms for clarity. (b) Isodensity representation (side view) of an extra hole introduced into the system (see main text). (c) Isodensity representation (side view) of hole trapping on surface V_{Pb}^0 . The triiodide formed upon displacement of a surface I atom (*cf.* main text) is circled and, for clarity, MA molecules are not shown.

In contrast to this, V_{I} does not feature mid-gap states and apparently does not represent an issue for recombination at the surface. However, structural and electronic analysis reveals a mechanism that could possibly affect charge transfer at the surface. In fact, in surface V_{I}^+ , the under-coordinated Pb atoms are found to move far from the vacancy, while two I atoms get closer to each other by ~ 0.3 Å. Consequently, the associated Pb–I bonds are elongated [*cf.* Fig. 5(a)]. Analysis of the VBM of the system in the $+1$ charge state shows that the observed bond elongation and the presence of the positively charged defect prevent the formation of the surface hole polaron in the plane featuring V_{I}^+ . For instance, the surface hole polaron, observed for the pristine PbI_2 slab [*cf.* Fig. 2(c)], is not found on the terminal PbI_2 plane featuring V_{I} but on a sub-surface plane [*cf.* Fig. 5(b)]. Therefore, the Pb–I bond elongations associated with V_{I} destabilize hole polarons suggesting that, while not acting as a recombination centre, surface V_{I} may slow down or even inhibit the migration of the hole polaron to the surface, possibly affecting interfacial charge transfer.

Fig. 5 (a) Top view of the surface reconstruction on the PbI_2 plane of the (001) surface of tetragonal MAPbI_3 for V_{I} in the $+1$ charge state. We only show one plane of Pb and I atoms for clarity. (b) Isodensity representation of the VBM for the PbI_2 surface (side view) bearing a V_{I} in the -1 charge state. The position of the vacancy is highlighted in the figure.

We next investigate the energetics of formation of surface interstitial iodine, I_{i} , which may appear in three different charged states: $+1$, 0 , and -1 . For the MAI surface, we observe that I_{i}^+ is remarkably less stable than in the bulk, as the formation energy of the defect is found to be 0.25 eV higher [*cf.* Fig. 6(a)]. A similar trend is observed also for the neutral defect (not shown). This is consistent with the previously observed tendency of hole polarons to not localize on this surface termination. The energy difference is slightly reduced when considering the -1 state, but the bulk defect is still favoured. In contrast, surface I_{i} is more stable on the PbI_2 termination, particularly for the charge states envisaging localization of positive charge on the surface (0 and $+1$), in accord with its capability of attracting hole polarons. As a consequence, the charge transition level $\mu(+1/-1)$ is shifted towards lower (higher) energy values for the MAI (PbI_2) surfaces [*cf.* Fig. 6(a)]. We note that a previous study on the bulk I_{i} has proved that recombination of holes and electrons is prevented by the combined effects of (i) a kinetic barrier for hole trapping on the defect and (ii)

a reduced interaction between the positive charge and the negatively charged iodine defect, the latter being mainly induced by the fast hopping of the hole polaron within the material.²⁷ We here observe that, upon injection of a hole in the surface I_i^- , the injected positive charge localizes as a bulk-like (surface) hole polaron for the MAI (PbI_2) surface [cf. Fig. 6(c) for I_i^- on the PbI_2 surface]. Therefore, the formation of the Pb-bridging I_2^- dimer, associated with the I_i^0 defect [cf. Fig. 6(b) for I_i^0 on the PbI_2 surface] implies the overcoming of an energy barrier also for the surface defect. We here employ a modified linear transit method²² (cf. Section 2) and we estimate energy barriers for the reaction $I_i^- + h^+ \rightarrow I_i^0$ of 0.10 and 0.20 eV for the PbI_2 and MAI surface, respectively, close to the value previously calculated for the bulk.²⁷ While the calculated barriers are small if compared to intrinsic errors in DFT calculations, we note that the calculated formation energies of surface I_i indicate that such defects are present in lower densities on the MAI surface than in the bulk $MAPbI_3$. Furthermore, the hole trapping on the defect at the MAI surface is prevented not only by the presence of an energy barrier but also by the preferential localization of holes in the bulk-like region of the slab for this surface termination [cf. Fig. 2(a)]. For these reasons, we expect that this defect plays only a marginal role in the surface recombination processes. In contrast to this, I_i on the PbI_2 surface is more stable than the bulk defect and the pinning of the hole polaron on the terminal PbI_2 layer [cf. Fig. 2(c)] increases the probability of interaction with the negatively charged defect and consequently that of overcoming the small energy barrier, thus ultimately enhancing the monomolecular recombination.

Fig. 6 (a) Formation energies of I_i as a function of the electron chemical potential on the MAI (blue dotted) and PbI_2 (red solid) (001) $MAPbI_3$ surfaces. Black dashed line for the respective values calculated for the bulk material. We consider iodine medium conditions as estimated in ref. 82, which correspond to $\mu_{MA} = -1.71$ eV, $\mu_{Pb} = -1.43$ eV, $\mu_I = -0.81$ eV. The conduction band edge is placed on the energy diagram by adding the experimental band gap⁸³ of $MAPbI_3$ to the valence band edge. Side view of the PbI_2 -terminated (001) surface of $MAPbI_3$ containing (b) the negatively charged interstitial I_i^- and a hole polaron (left panel) and (c) the neutral I_i^0 forming the I_2^- dimer (centre panel). Isodensity representation of the hole is given in shaded purple.

Overall, the present results allow us to rationalize some of the practices adopted to limit the recombination of charge carriers at the interface and reconcile contrasting results previously reported. In Fig. 6, we report the relevant energy levels calculated for surface polarons and surface defects on the (001) MAI and PbI_2 slabs of tetragonal $MAPbI_3$. First, surface termination determines a preferential localization of hole and electron polarons, with the former localizing on the PbI_2 surface and the latter on the MAI one. Analysis of a system with a partial MAI coverage suggests that rough surfaces would open recombination channels within the material, due to the increased interaction between charge carriers, and could imply a possible degradation mechanism of the surface. The analysis of surface defects for the MAI system indicates that the only defect which is stabilized with respect to the bulk is V_{MA} (cf. Fig. 3), which however still gives a shallow charge transition level (cf. Fig. 7). The substantial preservation of the defect tolerance typical of the bulk material for the MAI surface model is in agreement with measurements that relate the reduced charge recombination in polycrystalline samples with excess MA cations passivating the surface.³⁷ In contrast, the results achieved for the PbI_2 model evidence that the unsaturated Pb and I surface atoms are subject to substantial displacements. This, in turn, stabilizes the surface defects and causes either the formation of

surface recombination centres (V_{Pb} , I_i) or defects which is disadvantageous for charge localization at the surface (*i.e.* V_i , *cf.* Fig. 4). The simultaneous high stabilities of surface V_{Pb} and I_i and the preferential localization of hole polarons on the PbI_2 surface make these defects possible monomolecular recombination centres. Therefore, while our results on the polaron localization confirm that the pristine PbI_2 surfaces would not favour recombination since we observe charge localization similar to that attained in the bulk,^{40,41} the enhanced trapping properties of V_{Pb} and I_i observed for this termination suggest that MAI-rich conditions should be preferred to reduce defect activity at the surface. Finally, we note that the two different terminations possess largely different work functions (*cf.* Fig. 7 and *ref.* 49) and, therefore, the alignment between $MAPbI_3$ and the charge transfer layers within the actual photovoltaic device should be taken into account for the design of novel architectures.

Fig. 7 Schematic representation of the energy levels of surface defects which are relevant for the MAI and PbI_2 terminations of the (001) surface of tetragonal $MAPbI_3$. All energy levels are referred to the vacuum level, considering the work functions calculated in *ref.* 49. The conduction band edge is placed on the energy diagram by adding the experimental band gap⁸³ of $MAPbI_3$ to the valence band edge.

4. Summary and conclusions

In summary, our results evidenced that the separate localization of charge carriers for pristine and flat surface MAI and PbI_2 terminations is perturbed when considering mixed and rough surfaces that experimentally showed higher recombination. The study of surface defects showed that MAI surfaces are as defect tolerant as the bulk system, thus suggesting that MAI rich conditions of growth are preferable to reduce monomolecular recombination at the surface. In contrast, the PbI_2 surface needs to be passivated as it features defects that could enhance recombination or limit interfacial charge transfer. We hope that these results will serve as a guideline to further optimize the performance and temporal stability of lead-halide perovskites for optoelectronic applications.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 764047 of the ESPRESSO project and by the European Union project PERT PV under grant agreement No. 763977. The Ministero dell'Istruzione dell'Università e della Ricerca (MIUR) and Università degli Studi di Perugia are acknowledged for financial support through the program "Dipartimenti di Eccellenza 2018–2022" (Grant AMIS) to F. D. A.

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